

A Comparative Analysis of Job Creation and New-Age Tourism Techniques, Pre and Post-Covid 19 - A Phenomenological Study

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ABSTRACT:

The youth of today who were planning for their career advancements were highly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. During this time, the youth's education also suffered, giving rise to a 'lockdown generation' that will have to bear the burden of the crisis for a very long time. Many have experienced certain difficulties and challenges in the decision-making process after becoming unemployed during the crisis. The paper thus aims to examine the development of youth and the growth of new-age tourism techniques post-COVID-19 pandemic. The paper will also compare the pre and post-development of the tourism industry and what are the new tourism techniques that are adopted for generating employment.

KEYWORDS: entrepreneurship, job creation, tourism development, covid 19, youth, marketing

INTRODUCTION:

Job creation is something that provides a person with different opportunities in a specific field with salary, but due to the unavoidable fact of COVID-19, the youth of today's generation are immensely affected in the field of employment or job creation which has become one of the challenging issues globally. Youths who were involved in career planning at the time of the lockdown phase have experienced certain difficulties and challenges in the decision-making process and some youths have become unemployed during the crisis. To consider the serious situation, this topic has been chosen and elaborated on throughout the paper.

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on the employment prospects of young people. During this time, the youth's education also suffered, giving rise to a "lockdown generation" that will have to bear the burden of the crisis for a very long time. They were most severely impacted by the crisis both economically and socially. They faced difficulties with unemployment even before the pandemic. Their education was put on hold during this time, so they lacked knowledge and training experience in the field of study that they had chosen.

According to the findings of various studies, the unemployment rate in 13 countries increased by the end of 2020, even doubling the rate in a few cases.

The COVID-19 outbreak in recent years has brought about an unprecedented crisis among the world's population. The world was put on "lockdown" as a result of it. People had to deal with several difficulties as an outcome of the lockdown situation, including post-traumatic stress disorder after the pandemic, the death of loved ones, unemployment, isolation, and suspension of education throughout the pandemic era. The pandemic's outbreak had several detrimental effects on young people. The main one was the pre-covid period's suspension of education. Although it has made online education a standardised procedure of learning and teaching, it has also put pressure on students to adapt to online learning patterns that many people find difficult to do effectively. Consequently, they were unable to apply what they had learned to real-world situations, as they had to comprehend their subjects independently and were unable to show interest in or commitment to their studies. Their respective fields of employment suffered as a result of their inability to obtain the required education, training, or experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In their paper, **A. Maritz et al. (2020)** seek to offer entrepreneurship insights, implementations, and dynamics to illustrate the function of entrepreneurship in such challenging circumstances within an Australian context. They present narratives of emergent research from eminent Australian academics, highlighting the role of entrepreneurial initiatives in the emergence and expansion of new businesses. Insights related to the entrepreneurial mindset, the multifaceted effects of entrepreneurship and resilience, entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship enablers, and the entrepreneurial ecosystem are all covered in the narratives.

In their paper, **M. Nungsari et al. (2022)** investigate how young people view an informal online EET programme that was run during the pandemic. Perceptions are important because they frequently lead to attitudes, which may then result in either achieving or failing to achieve learning objectives.

By examining the following categories, **L. J. Gashi & E. K. (2022)** investigate how young people made career decisions during the pandemic. These categories include possible effects of the pandemic on emotional, social, and professional aspects; support from family, school, and peers; challenges and difficulties experienced during the career planning process; and the need and opportunities for career guidance. The authors conducted one-on-one interviews with thirty high school seniors in the 12th grade using Google Meet. The results of the thematic analysis showed that the participants had difficulty making career decisions during the pandemic. Their emotional and social states were impacted by worries about abrupt adjustments to daily routines and restrictive measures. Participants claimed that their families had provided them with enough support, but neither their schools nor their peers did. They said it would be helpful if their schools or other institutions offered information on career orientation. The study's conclusions emphasise the need for schools to have a formal, structured career orientation programme.

S. C. Santos et al. (2023) investigate how digital technologies reinvented entrepreneurial resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the digital artefacts, platforms, and infrastructures used by entrepreneurs to demonstrate entrepreneurial resilience. 42 reflective interviews with eminent businesspeople from the How I Built This "Resilience Series" podcast were analysed in the paper to examine how businesspeople handled the COVID-19 crisis. The study used a systematic approach to identify and describe digitalization-related behaviours, actions, and strategies for reinventing business in the uncertain and resource-constrained context of COVID-19.

RESEARCH GAP:

According to the literature review, there is a theoretical gap between post-COVID-19 tourism job vacancies, trends, existing manoeuvres, and policies. The majority of the research focuses on post-COVID-19 experiences, obstacles, trend shifts, technical developments, new product-specific

marketing strategies, and so on. The goal of this study is to find new job opportunities in the tourism industry for youths from various educational backgrounds.

OBJECTIVES:

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the post-COVID employment generation of youth as well as to identify new-age tourism tools and techniques.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research is an analysis of previous year's papers, certain websites, newspaper articles and YouTube videos on unemployment due to COVID-19 as well as the resurgence of new age job creation post-COVID with new tools and techniques with a special focus on the tourism sector.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PRE AND POST COVID DEVELOPMENT IN TOURISM

Unemployment of Youth in India Post COVID-19

During the early months of COVID-19, economies struggled to maintain their strength while dealing with the health-care crisis and other major issues such as unemployment, which was a major concern for approximately 27 countries.

Similar, albeit more alarming, events took place in India. The sudden containment imposed across the country resulted in people being confined to their homes in a matter of days. Many people were abruptly removed from the job market due to the pandemic. If we go back three years, the labour market was already weak before the outbreak, with high unemployment brought on by the downturn in the economy. The problem was more severely made worse by the pandemic. Many Indian youths who had just graduated were denied the chance to land a good job due to the 2020 lockdown. Even students from elite institutions like IIMs and IITs had their job offers withdrawn or postponed, forcing them to look for alternative employment opportunities. Nearly half of the young people working in the four industries hardest hit by the pandemic—manufacturing, rental

and business services, accommodation and food services—were a significant factor in the youth experiencing labour market disruption and job losses.

Unemployment of Youth in India Post COVID-19 (2021)

Data was collected from an article published on the Times of India's official website.

(<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/krishna-athal/youth-unemployment-in-india-post-covid-19/>)

Job-Skill Requirements in Different Sectors After Covid 19

Several industries, including technology, pharmacy, finance, healthcare, online retail, teleworking communications, grocery, shipping, education, and others, saw high demand during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Skilled workers are in demand across industries after Covid 19. The following are just a few of the highly sought-after professions today: data management, cloud computing, virtual and augmented reality, web development, cyber security, digital education, AI specialists, health care, public safety, social and digital media marketing, legal services, counselling, conceptualization, and coding.

The Pre-Pandemic Era's Growth of the Tourism Industry

Before the pandemic, the tourism sector was one of the most successful and important for the world economy. 2019 marked the tenth year in a row that the tourism industry experienced sustainable growth (World Tourism Organisation). The highest growth in arrivals was seen in the Middle East region. The Middle East, Europe, and Asia were the top geographical areas to see increases in tourism revenue. The top travel destinations for people in 2019 were France, Spain, the United States, China, and Italy (United Nations World Tourism Organisation, 2020).

People travel for a variety of reasons. Some go on business, while others go on vacation to unwind and avoid engaging in more stressful activities. In light of these factors, it is important to note that, according to UNWTO reports, tourism experienced significant growth in the years before the pandemic. Other industries like transportation, lodging, hospitality, and food & beverages are impacted by the tourism industry. It seems that the expansion of tourism as an industry during the period before the pandemic situation led to a decent advancement in revenue in these supporting industries.

Post-COVID Tourism Rebound

According to the International Labour Organisation, over 114 million jobs were lost globally in 2020 (International Labour Organisation, 2021). Governmental restrictions on such activities led to the closure of businesses that required people to travel and engage in social activities. These incidents were crucial in the decline of the tourism sector and related industries (S. Sunder and S. Dixit, 2023).

In 2022, over 900 million people travelled abroad, which is more than double the number from 2021 but still 37% less than in 2019. According to UNWTO's scenarios published in May 2022, international tourism returned to 63% of its pre-pandemic levels. Nearly 80% of pre-pandemic levels were reached by the world's top destination region, Europe, in 2022 with 585 million arrivals (a decrease of 11% from 2019). When compared to other regions, the Middle East saw the largest relative increase in 2022, with arrivals rising to 83% of pre-pandemic levels (-17% from 2019). Due to more stringent pandemic-related restrictions, Asia and the Pacific only reached 23% of

their pre-pandemic visitors while Africa and the Americas both recovered about 65% (UNWTO, 2023).

In 2023, as travel costs rise, travellers will look for more genuine and distinctive travel experiences that are worth their money. People will continue to travel to visit friends and family and to feel a sense of belonging. Hoteliers and destination management companies may highlight their specials as a chance to make enduring family memories. When asking for their offers, it can be more effective to use a picture of a smiling family than one of a vacant hotel room or deserted beach (C. Heo).

The destination market had reached saturation during the pre-pandemic phase as a means of promoting travel destinations. The main cause of this stagnation is thought to be the overcrowding of some exotic locations as opposed to some unknown paths. As a result, many tourist attractions that used this tactic to promote themselves saw a decline in visitors. However, destination marketing as a strategy has reemerged and is having a significant impact on the market because people stopped going to these places altogether during the pandemic. This strategy's success has also been greatly influenced by social media (S. Sunder and S. Dixit, 2023). When promoting their locations, influencers, brands, businesses, etc. use social media sites like Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok, among others. Over 70% of travellers are estimated to use smartphones for travel research, according to a recent Google study (Think with Google, 2016). With the aid of an emotional hook, interested parties can use this statistic to increase their visibility on social media platforms and draw travellers with like-minded needs, desires, and motivations. This tactic has a high rate of conversion and is promoting travel both regionally and globally.

Professionals who adopted the "work-from-home" philosophy during the pandemic had a great opportunity to both work and stay at home. The tourism sector underwent numerous changes as a result of this policy.

People began travelling and operating out of cafes, restaurants, hotels, etc. It's not entirely unusual for people to be able to add to their work while constantly moving around. Even though it is not a typical method of working, it has been used before. The rise, however, started during the early

pandemic waves when the IT industry offered all-inclusive tools to help businesses conduct their operations from remote locations (S. Sunder and S. Dixit, 2023).

New-Age Tourism Tools and Techniques

Robotics: The working conditions in the majority of factories around the world, are one of the main reasons why the work zones were completely shut down during the pandemic. There is no room to use social distance for assembly line tasks, for which there is a large number of migrant workers who come for work from different cities as well as countries. These workers had to be sent home, and factories had to be closed. This had an impact on the lives of manufacturing industry workers as well as the output, production, and supply of goods produced. Such problems can be resolved as a result of the development of robotics. These kinds of technologies can be used to automate robotically performing manual tasks without endangering the lives of people. Hyundai Robotics established a team to manufacture robots that assist people in taking glory in data development and data literacy, as well as space planning, autonomous driving, and voice recognition (Noonwal. et al., 2022). According to Zeng et al. (2020), the hospitality industry is served by fourteen robots employed by the robotics company Cloud Minds. Drones that were originally used to spray pesticides on agriculture fields have been repurposed to spray disinfectants in areas heavily visited by tourists in scenic areas. Unlike flat city roads, the complex terrain of many scenic areas makes it difficult for larger car-like robots to manage the disinfection. To more effectively track the volume and movement of tourists in a scenic area, drones are also used to provide an overhead view. Further, Meituan Dianping (a major food delivery company) used service robots in its partner restaurants to deliver food from kitchens to patrons and delivery personnel in February 2020 in Beijing, according to Toh and Wang (2020).

Employers are increasingly using automation, including robots, rather than calling back existing employees or hiring new ones as the U.S. economy recovers from the COVID-19 pandemic. To disinfect airport facilities, mobile robots have been used in place of the janitors' original use of

moon suits and other personal protective equipment. The Pennsylvania Turnpike switched from a cash-based system to a cashless electronic one, eliminating manual toll collection.

According to the Association for Advancing Automation, orders for robots in North America, primarily the U.S., increased by 20% in the first quarter compared to the same period in 2018 and by 16% from the same three-month period in 2019, which was well before the pandemic. According to statistics, the fourth quarter of 2020 saw the second-best quarter ever for orders of robots at close to 10,000 (Los Angeles Times).

“COVID had just brought attention to the possibility that some of this could accelerate due to potential business interruptions” (Mark Lewandowski, director of robotics innovation for P&G, 2021).

According to Camilleri (2017), the majority of tourism workers lack adequate training in technological usage, which causes them to feel uneasy, anxious, and frustrated when robots are used in service or production. Technology anxiety, according to Lee and Cranage (2017), can make people anxious and distressed at work and interfere with their normal day-to-day activities. The tourism and hospitality industries experienced a sharp decline in job opportunities during the COVID-19 crisis, which had an adverse effect on the workers' psychological and physical well-being, social standing, and organisational involvement as well as amplified their anxiety and depression (Aguilar-Quintana et al., 2021).

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning: The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in the tourism sector has been accelerated after COVID-19 due to the industry's need to adapt to new challenges and customer preferences. Businesses and nations around the world are working to rebuild their resilience in the event of similar scenarios in the future. Most people's eyes have been opened about how important it is to bring about change as a result of the COVID-19 situation. One essential component of that desired change is tech knowledge. More and more businesses are attempting to adopt technologies to protect themselves from such a breakdown and continue operating normally. A significant component of this technological advancement is artificial intelligence, the Internet of things, and machine learning.

B.Tech students with these specialisations or backgrounds will therefore be in high demand. AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants provide instant customer support and information (Chi et al., 2020). AI analyses social media and geolocation data to understand tourist behaviour, helping destinations plan infrastructure and services. ML models predict the impact of crises, aiding authorities' inefficient resource allocation during emergencies (Sigala, M., 2020).

Digital Transformer: The reliance on digital technologies has increased dramatically across all sectors, including business, education, hospitality, small businesses, restaurants, etc. Today, a large number of software service providers help their clients on their journeys through digital transformation. A huge part of the digital transformation is played by everything from creating apps to establishing blockchain and cloud technologies. This is especially true in the wake of the pandemic era. The implications of COVID-19 on tourism, including the rise of contactless technologies for various touchpoints in the industry. Mobile apps for contactless check-ins, digital payments, and self-service kiosks to minimise physical contact (Sigala, M., 2020).

Today, knowing a visitor's age, country of origin, or sex is no longer sufficient for the tourism industry; you also need to know what they like and what interests them to keep them interested and encourage them to return. How? Open data for big data. The importance of gathering and examining as much data from their customers as possible must be understood by tourism businesses in order to better understand them and be able to cater to their preferences and personalities. These days, it's crucial that customers not only come back but also share their experiences on social media to encourage other users to travel to those locations. They are used by businesses of all sizes, from large corporations to SMEs or start-ups, as a tool for communication, building customer loyalty, and even for customer service. In a short period of time, the number of profiles focused on more personalised travel recommendations has increased. The process of digitization also affects the various sites, which transform into open, accessible, intelligent destinations that encourage interaction and integration between visitors and locals as well as within the local population. (TILEAGĂ 2022).

Entrepreneurship: Due to their lack of readiness for this unexpected change in the world, many small businesses have closed. But that still leaves plenty of room for future business owners who envision themselves launching new ventures. Because they have witnessed the widespread effects of an epidemic, they are now better equipped to build a more resilient company that can withstand disruptions in the future.

South Africa was one of the countries to pay social assistance to people who were unemployed and had no other source of income during the pandemic. The amount was small, roughly 20 euros a month, which sparked controversy. But it helped many survive, and a few to even start a new business. Event photography, that's what Thando Makhobo did before COVID struck, but after almost all events were cancelled, he had to find new subjects to photograph. He saved about 40 euros from his COVID grants to come up with creative ice cream designs. The pictures posted on his social media channels went viral and he decided to open an ice cream parlour, in his mother's house. On good days he makes more than 1,000 euros. Up to 200 customers find their way to his home in the subway to a township and almost everyone here heard about the place online (DW News, 2022).

For some the pandemic created business opportunities, like employees of Ugandan start-up Rocket Health. The telemedicine company offers health services via phone or internet connecting patients to doctors and hospitals. At this call-centre in Uganda, doctors consult with patients virtually. In Uganda, a large number of people lack access to routine medical care. Others simply reside too far away. Lockdowns caused by the pandemic make doctor visits even more challenging, and in-person visits also increase the risk of infection. A health care provider is one of the first confirmed COVID cases in Uganda. Following months passed. There were many infected frontline healthcare workers. Most people kept their jobs, but they were concerned for their families. Working from home for doctors can relieve pressure on overburdened hospitals and lower the risk of exposure to the Coronavirus for doctors, patients, and their contacts (DW News, 2022).

Marketing: The COVID acted as a motivating factor to overcome the psychological barrier preventing acceptance of the new fashion. These new difficulties and requirements would produce

skilled marketing specialists who could plan, create, and design new marketing strategies for businesses.

The ability to more effectively personalise every aspect of marketing strategies in order to target new markets is one of the biggest advantages of digitalization. The most difficult and time-consuming part of a vacation is planning the trip. Many people find it difficult to decide between the convenience of the hotel and the access to the most intriguing tourist attractions because everyone has distinct tastes and experiences. As a result, market tourism demands constant options that are tailored to its specific requirements (TILEAGĂ, 2022). Traveller preferences, interests, seasonality, sustainability, and other factors have all become more important as destination management strategies have evolved and become more sophisticated. Previously, destination marketing and figures based on arrival numbers were the focus of tourism boards. The days of universally applicable, cookie-cutter travel strategies are long gone (Adriana, 2021).

FINDINGS & DISCUSSION:

Because the potential traveller contributes valuable information to the value chain at every stage of the interest-generation, purchasing, and post-purchase processes—he is an active traveller—the new digital tourist intervenes and co-creates the destinations. Currently, the trips are experienced three times: first, during their election and preparation; second, as they gain experience; and third, when they are being counted. To fully comprehend the client, the information provided during these three stages is crucial. Thanks to the digital environment and new technologies, it is possible to more precisely meet the demand with the information obtained. In parallel, there is an increase in the use of cameras, the internet of things, contactless interaction, and biometrics. The productivity of businesses has greatly benefited from these clever innovations. They simultaneously enhanced the visitor experience and raised the value earned. (TILEAGĂ, 2022). One can't please everyone, so by delving deeper into the narratives that matter for particular market segments, one must remember that places that seek to satisfy

everyone run the risk of providing nothing of value to anyone. The biggest marketing effects frequently result from investments in specialised traveller interests.

CONCLUSION:

The history of tourism has seen many crises, but none have ever been as severe as the Covid 19. Resuming tourist activity will require industry-wide technological advancements. Thanks to technological advancements, this industry has a great growth potential. However, the shift is now a requirement for both customers and businesses. The client currently possesses a vast amount of knowledge, making it necessary to tailor the services provided. The organisation's sustainability and growth depend on digital transformation. Artificial intelligence and augmented reality will be used more frequently thanks to new technology.

For employees to fit into new and unexpected roles, managers must plan and anticipate the need for retraining and upskilling. For workers to become more competent over time, they urgently need to develop both critical and recently discovered skills. Higher-order cognitive, social, emotional, and digital skills, as well as higher levels of adaptability, resilience, and empathy, may be among the crucial abilities needed for the future (Agha., 2022). A significant improvement over earlier practices can be seen in the manner in which work is being completed during and after COVID-19. Large multinational corporations that had previously shied away from allowing employees to work remotely are now shifting their philosophies to make remote working the new norm. When working remotely, there are numerous advantages for both employers and employees. However, in order to implement this new routine, the entire system of managing the workforce, measuring productivity, allocating leaves, conducting mental health checks, and benefit mechanisms must be redesigned. To overcome the psychological barrier preventing acceptance of the new fashion, COVID-19 served as a motivating factor. The new challenges and demands would result in knowledgeable marketing specialists who could plan, design, and develop fresh marketing strategies for companies.

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